
IDEAS-QA4EO

WP-2520: Support to SRIX4Veg

**D-1 & D-2 Report on the SRIX4Veg fieldwork activities,
processing workflows and data utilisation**

D-3 Orthorectified surface reflectance products

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Contributors: Magdalena Smigaj, Jens van der Zee,
Harm Bartholomeus, Lammert Kooistra

Affiliation: Laboratory of Geon-information Science and Remote Sensing,
Wageningen University, the Netherlands

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1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This document is the report of IDEAS-QA4EO WP-2520, covering activities undertaken as part of the Surface Reflectance Intercomparison Exercise for Vegetation (SRIX4Veg) initiative. SRIX4Veg is an activity endorsed by the Committee on Earth Observation Satellites (CEOS), designed to inform the creation of global community-agreed guidelines for surface reflectance product validation with Unoccupied Aerial Vehicles (UAVs). Its main aim is to determine the expected variance in UAV-derived surface reflectance data (for the validation of satellite surface reflectance products) collected under the same nominal conditions (location and time) caused by the operational variation by different teams. This document covers field activities undertaken as part of the SRIV4Veg fieldwork campaign in July 2022 in Barrax, Spain and subsequent data pre-processing and post-processing workflows (deliverables D1, D2 and D3).

2 SRIX4Veg field campaign

2.1 UAV hyperspectral system

As part of the SRIX4Veg field campaign UAV-derived surface reflectance products acquired from different systems, as provided by different project partners (including Wageningen University), were compared. The UAV system assembled at Wageningen University and subsequently used in this project comprises a DJI Matrice 300 platform, a Headwall Nano Hyperspec VNIR camera and a Velodyne VLP-16 LiDAR sensor as shown in Figure 1. DJI Matrice 300 (DJI, Shenzhen, China) is a hexacopter with a maximum take-off weight (MTOW) of up to 9 kg, offering a maximum payload capacity of up to 2.7 kilograms. The platform was selected based on its performance, allowing long flight times (compared to larger platforms such as DJI M600) of approximately 30 minutes under MTOW. Additionally, the platform is equipped with a Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) GNSS system, which enhances the positioning reliability and accuracy down to centimetre level. The main instrument deployed onboard was a Headwall Nano Hyperspec VNIR (Headwall Photonics, Bolton, MA, USA) camera with a 12 mm lens and 22° field of view. The Headwall Nano Hyperspec VNIR is a pushbroom imaging spectrometer, which operates in the visible and near-infrared (VNIR) regions from 400 to 1000 nm. It has 270 spectral bands, 640 spatial bands, and a spectral resolution of 2.2 nm. To overcome the lack of off-the-shelf solutions for the selected DJI M300 platform, a custom mounting system was developed in-house to host the hyperspectral sensor. The weight and space limitations prevented deployment of a gimbal system that could help compensate for the UAV movements in-flight. Instead, a hard mounting solution was constructed with use of aluminium plates. Within the mount, a series of adjustment screws were

incorporated with which the camera angle can be adjusted prior to the acquisition; this ensures the camera system is levelled with respect to the UAV's centre of mass. The mounting solution can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Hyperspectral UAV system with a custom-mounted Headwall Nano Hyperspec VNIR camera and a Velodyne VLP-16 LiDAR (*left*), alongside the field procedure for optimising the radiometric range of the hyperspectral imager based on white panel observations (*right*).

The UAV system was supplemented with an Applanix APX-15 GNSS/inertial measuring unit (IMU) that enables highly accurate tracking of the flight trajectory and UAV platform movements; this information is subsequently used for georeferencing and image orthorectification purposes. Additionally, the UAV system hosts a double return Velodyne VLP-16 laser scanner (Velodyne Acoustics, Inc., Morgan Hill, CA, USA), which also relies on the Applanix APX-15 GNSS/IMU observations for georeferencing purposes. Utilisation of same trajectory observations allows potential offsets between the hyperspectral and the LiDAR datasets to be minimised. The LiDAR scanner has a maximum range of 80–100 m and produces three-dimensional laser point cloud data with 16 laser beams per scan at 30° vertical field of view and 360° horizontal field of view.

2.2 UAV hyperspectral system testing

Following the system assembly, initial pre-campaign testing was undertaken over grass experimental field trial in Wageningen, the Netherlands (51°59'45"N, 5°39'21"E, Figure 2). The trial comprised a range of grass varieties undergoing varied irrigation and mowing treatments, consequently offering good variation in spectral responses. A flight campaign utilising the UAV hyperspectral system was undertaken on 16th June 2022, during which a total of 6 flightlines of hyperspectral imagery with a Ground Sampling Distance (GSD) of 2.4 cm were obtained. The collected data was processed to surface Hemispherical-Conical Reflectance Factor (HCRF) with use of reference targets, georeferenced and orthorectified. The georeferencing and orthorectification relied on UAV trajectory information

provided by the APX-15 GPS/IMU unit and a high-resolution Digital Surface Model (DSM) of the Wageningen grassland study area.

Figure 2: Hyperspectral orthomosaic (2.4 cm spatial resolution) of the grass experimental site with locations of field spectral measurements marked with black circles and ground control targets marked in white (*left*), alongside an example intercomparison between field-measured (black lines) and image-derived spectra (colour lines) – shaded areas represent one standard deviation (*right*).

Immediately following the flight, field spectral measurements of 12 visually different grass parcels were collected with Tec5 MMS1 for comparison purposes. Tec5 MMS1 is equipped with VNIR spectrometers, measuring across the 400-1000 nm region, that simultaneously measure the incident downwelling and upwelling radiation. The instrument is mounted on a pole at the height of 163 cm, which in the trial resulted in a spot size with a diameter of 72.3 cm. Average image reflectance factors for corresponding measurement locations were derived and compared against the field measurements; the intercomparison revealed good agreement with mean average error of 1.4% across all bands – example spectra are shown in Figure 2. The largest disagreement was found in the 900-1000 nm range where the sensor's signal to noise ratio is the poorest due to its inherent properties.

To assess the image geometric quality and accuracy of georeferencing, 10 Ground Control Points (GCPs) were deployed throughout the survey area as shown in Figure 2. Exact locations of these GCPs were measured on the ground using GNSS RTK positioning and compared against corresponding image coordinates. The assessment indicated that although centimetre-level relative positional precision, i.e.

internal image geometry, can be achieved relying on the GNSS/IMU unit, supplementary GCPs are needed for highly accurate georeferencing; within the acquired dataset an offset of 40 cm in the XY direction was present. Similar offsets of 10-40 cm were observed in datasets collected with the system since.

2.3 SRIX4Veg campaign set-up

The assembled UAV hyperspectral system was utilised during the SRIX4Veg UAV campaign, which took place in the week of 18th July 2022 at Las Tiasas experimental farm near Barrax, Spain. The selected site was established in 1999 and met the main Fiducial Reference Measurement (FRM) requirements for satellite validation purposes, including flat, large and uniform land-use units that are representative of different crop types, good accessibility, and 90% likelihood of clear skies in July. In total, seven teams took part in the SRIX4Veg exercise, and were tasked to acquire UAV hyperspectral imagery according to two protocols over a common area of 60 x 60 m where maize was planted (39° 2'56"N, 2° 4'38"W, Figure 3); this area is consistent with 3 x 3 pixels at 20 m resolution of Sentinel 2. In the neighbouring barren field, a series of ground calibration targets were deployed on top of wooden pallets; these included a single calibration tarpaulin manufactured by Headwall and a series of Permaflect targets, both of which offered three brightness levels (Figure 3). Immediately before and after each flight, Fieldspec 4 spectrometer measurements of the deployed targets were performed to enable radiometric calibration. Additionally, next to the calibration targets, a GNSS base station was deployed for collection of reference positioning information.

Figure 3: UAV data acquisition area highlighted in yellow within which the 60 x 60 m maize crop plot is included (*left*) and example UAV image of the deployed reference targets (*right*).

2.4 Hyperspectral data acquisition

To test the amount of variance in surface reflectance data resulting from different measurement approaches, two separate experiments were conducted by each participating team. For the first experiment a standardised protocol developed by FRM4Veg team was employed, whereas for the second experiment an in-house approach as regularly adopted by individual partners for data collection was followed. The main flight parameters and differences between the two employed protocols are summarised in Table 1. In both cases the hyperspectral imager was optimised to approximately 75% of the radiometric range to ensure that pixel saturation did not occur in any of the spectral bands, and orientation of the flight lines was set to 8.62° (calculated with respect to North) to ensure the same across track scanning between the Sentinel-2 MSI satellite sensor (98.62° orbit inclination) and the UAV-borne sensor. The main differences were the flying height, the flightline overlap.

Table 1. Main technical details of the data acquisition protocols employed during the SRIX4Veg campaign.

	Protocol 1	Protocol 2
Flight height AGL	60 m	50 m
Flight speed	3 m/s	3 m/s
Flightline orientation	8.62°	8.62°
Flightline overlap	70%	50 %
GSD	3.5 cm	3 cm
Number of flight lines	12	8
Flight time	12 minutes	10 minutes

The data acquisition campaign took place on the 19th, 20th and 21st July 2022. In total 6 datasets, 3 for each protocol, were collected immediately before and after the acquisitions of other teams participating in the SRIX4Veg exercise; this approach will allow direct comparisons to be made between consecutive measurements. In each executed flight plan the UAV system was programmed to pass over the deployed calibration targets at exactly the same height as the rest of the flight; the overflight took place both at the beginning and at the end of the flight. Example flight trajectories of the employed protocols are shown in Figure 4 whereas acquisition details for each undertaken flight are provided in Table 2.

Figure 4: Example recorded flight trajectories of the pre-defined Protocol 1 (*left*) and the in-house approach/Protocol 2 (*right*). Colours represent relative GPS times (from dark blue to yellow). At the beginning of each flight a series of manoeuvres, displayed in dark blue, that are required for IMU initialisation were undertaken.

Table 2. Technical details of the data acquisition protocols employed during the SRIX4Veg campaign.

Protocol 1	Flight number	1	2	3
	Date	19.07.2022	20.07.2022	20.07.2022
	Time	11:22	9:56	14:39
Protocol 2	Flight number	1	2	3
	Date	21.07.2022	21.07.2022	21.07.2022
	Time	9:30	14:06	17:06

Due to the lack of phone reception in the study area, the platform’s RTK positioning feature could not be utilised, affecting the absolute flight positioning accuracy and the resultant data coverage. Additionally, harsh weather conditions – the campaign took place in the middle of a heatwave with air temperatures nearing 40°C – affected the hyperspectral sensor’s performance during one of the flights (flight 2 of Protocol 2 undertaken at 14:06 on 21st July 2022). Multiple detectors of the sensor recorded abnormal radiance measurements throughout several flightlines. This resulted in a bleeding effect on the imagery whereby the affected detectors recorded consistently low radiance throughout the spectrum irrespective of the target area; an example impacted flightline is shown in the Appendix A. The malfunction was discussed with the manufacturer who could not identify any direct cause. It is assumed that this abnormality was caused by potential system overheating. For quality reasons, this dataset was excluded from further processing and analysis. No irregularities were observed in datasets acquired during other flights.

3 SRIX4Veg data processing and delivery

3.1 Georeferencing and orthorectification

Georeferencing and orthorectification of the acquired hyperspectral and LiDAR data was based on UAV trajectories obtained from the APX-15 GNSS/IMU unit. The trajectories were post-processed relative to the observations from the base GNSS station deployed in the field to improve final positional accuracy; the use of a common base station additionally ensures consistency with other teams taking part in the SRIX4Veg campaign. The post-processed GNSS trajectories together with the IMU information and a local high resolution DSM were subsequently utilised for georeferencing and orthorectification purposes. For Protocol 1 a DSM supplied by the FRM4Veg team (created during a dedicated UAV LiDAR flight) was utilised, whereas for Protocol 2 a DSM derived from the co-obtained LiDAR dataset was used. During the orthorectification process, camera's pre-defined pitch, roll and yaw parameters were iteratively adjusted for each dataset to reduce the horizontal misalignment between individual flightlines, minimising relative horizontal errors to approximately 10 cm. Sample alignment results are shown in Figure 5. Since no GCPs were established for the SRIX4VEG campaign, absolute georeferencing accuracy could not be evaluated. However, previous experiences with the system indicated that without supplementary ground control, the absolute accuracy in the XY direction is expected to be within 50 cm.

Figure 5. Maize RGB field orthomosaics for sample datasets acquired under Protocol 1 (*left*) and Protocol 2 (*right*) composed of 12 and 8, respectively, co-aligned flightlines.

3.2 View Zenith Angle filtering

As a UAV platform moves through the air, the angle at which the imaging spectrometer points towards the ground varies, affecting the view zenith angle (VZA) of each pixel in the imagery. This effect is more pronounced in fixed-mount imaging spectrometers, such as the one used in this study, making them more vulnerable to wind gusts compared to gimballed imaging spectrometers. To compensate for these changes in sensor orientation, rotational information from the APX-15 GPS/IMU was utilised to derive VZA for each pixel across the entire dataset.

First, the angular field of view for each pixel based on the manufacturer's specifications for the installed lens was derived. With this information, we assumed a perfectly nadir viewing direction and determined the VZA for each pixel in the across-track direction. Next, information about the UAV platform's movement was incorporated into the VZA layer. Each scan line of the imagery was matched to the corresponding IMU readings based on timestamps embedded in both the imagery and IMU data. This allowed identifying the pitch, yaw, and roll angles experienced by the platform at each scan line. The roll angle, as measured by the IMU, was then added to the precalculated VZA for each pixel in each line of imagery. As part of the SRIX4Veg measurement protocol, this generated layer was subsequently used to mask pixels that fell outside the predefined VZA range of 3.5° to 8.5°. Figure 6 illustrates the workflow employed for an example flightline.

Figure 6. Workflow for VZA-based image masking. VZA layer calculations were based on camera's field of view and roll information derived from APX-15 GPS/IMU, and subsequent masking according to the 3.5° to 8.5° VZA range criterion.

Comparison of VZA-masked and non-masked imagery utilising the whole image swath at Sentinel-2 spatial resolution (following spectral convolution and spatial aggregation described in section 3.4) showed substantial differences in the resultant reflectance factor values, with the NIR region being most affected. On average, the differences were in the range of 0.1-0.2% for Sentinel-2 bands 2-5, increasing to 0.5-0.8% for Snetinel-2 bands 6-9 (see Appendix A). The largest discrepancies of up to 2.43% in the NIR region were observed in pixels where VZA masking led to substantial exclusion of shaded bare soil areas between maize rows.

3.3 Radiometric correction

Radiometric calibration was based on coincident ASD measurements of the deployed reference targets. Empirical line correction method was applied to each band for derivation of HCRF. The white panel of the calibration tarpaulin was excluded from the correction due to large spectral variation in the blue region. A close agreement between field ASD measurements of the other targets and image HCRF readings following the correction could be achieved as illustrated in Figure 7. The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) for all flights and targets throughout the spectrum was 0.72% (ranging from 0.69 to 0.81% across the flights) indicating close resemblance. The NIR region showed higher variability in the response due to the decreasing signal to noise ratio of the deployed sensor – this is particularly evident in the 900-1000 nm spectral range where the MAE increased to 1.14% (ranging from 0.93 to 1.45). Only minimal differences were present between the two employed protocols with main differences observable in the 900-100 nm range where Protocol 2 had MAE higher by 0.23%. Graphs for other executed flights are available in the Appendix A.

Figure 7. Comparison between image-derived reflectance factor (solid lines) and field spectrometer measurements (dashed lines) of ground calibration targets following empirical line calibration for two example datasets: flight 2 under Protocol 1 (*left*) and flight 1 under Protocol 2 (*right*).

3.4 Spectral convolution and spatial aggregation

The resultant imagery was processed to match the spectral response functions of Sentinel-2 imagery (provided by the FRM4Veg team) , following equation:

$$R(\lambda_b) = \frac{\int_{\lambda_{min}}^{\lambda_{max}} R_{UAS}(\lambda) S_{S2_i}(\lambda) d\lambda}{\int_{\lambda_{min}}^{\lambda_{max}} S_{S2_i}(\lambda) d\lambda}$$

where R is the output reflectance factor, R_{UAS} is the reflectance factor derived from the UAV at wavelength, λ , or in the Sentinel-2 band, λ_b , S_{S2} is the Sentinel-2 spectral response function for a specific band (i), and λ_{min} and λ_{max} are 400 nm and 1000 nm respectively.

The convolved imagery was subsequently aggregated to Sentinel-2 grid the supplied by the FRM4Veg team. To achieve this, all pixels falling within each grid square were averaged. Examples of the spatial aggregation outputs are shown in Figure 8. The resultant datasets have been used for intercomparison purposes with datasets obtained from other teams participating in the SRIX4Veg campaign. This comparison has highlighted the need for a common protocol to reduce variability in the obtained data.

Figure 8: Example visual results of the applied workflow for derivation of datasets reflective of Sentinel-2 products, including pixel masking (based on individual pixel's VZA information) and spatial/spectral aggregation. Respective images are displayed utilising RGB bands.

3.5 LiDAR data cleaning

Instability of the UAV during short periods of wind or when turning between flightlines can introduce noise into the LiDAR data and degrade the overall quality of the point cloud. These periods of instability were identified and subsequently removed from collected LiDAR datasets with the help of IMU data. IMU timestamps after which the yaw angle increased or decreased by more than 3 degrees over a period of 2 seconds were first flagged. Time intervals of significant yaw angle increase or decrease were then created from sequences of these labelled IMU timestamps. Any LiDAR points with timestamps that fell within these time intervals were subsequently removed. Finally, the point clouds were clipped to the extent of the hyperspectral data coverage.

4 Executive summary

4.1 Highlights

The WP-2520 resulted in a series of hyperspectral datasets and accompanying LiDAR point clouds collected during the SRIX4Veg field campaign. The survey was conducted over a maize field at Las Tiesas experimental farm near Barrax, Spain and followed two separate acquisition protocols with three flights undertaken according to each protocol. The collected datasets were georeferenced, orthorectified and radiometrically calibrated, and are available online as one of the deliverables of WP-2520. These were be further utilised for intercomparison purposes within the SRIX4Veg initiative (following VZA filtering, spectral convolution and spatial aggregation) to determine the expected variance in surface reflectance data due to operational variation by different project partners. These activities are currently forming basis for the creation of community-agreed guidelines for surface reflectance product validation with UAV systems (expected release in 2024).

4.2 Output data format

Hyperspectral imagery described in Section 2.4 and associated LiDAR datasets collected as part of the SRIX4Veg campaign will be made publicly available alongside this report. All datasets are provided as post-processed products following orthorectification (see Section 3.1), radiometric correction (see Section 3.3) and data cleaning (in the case of LiDAR, see Section 3.5). Although hyperspectral imagery from individual flightlines in each dataset were co-aligned as part of the data pre-processing, small misalignments (within 10 cm) are still present. To retain the original data quality, final datasets are provided as individual flightlines rather than a composite image.

The hyperspectral datasets have following properties:

- Measured quantity: HCRF
- Number of spectral bands: 260
- Spectral resolution: 2.2 nm
- Spatial resolution: sensor's nominal resolution
- File format: ENVI
- Format: float 32
- Coordinate system: EPSG 4326 – WGS84 reference ellipsoid
- NoData value: Nan
- Scaling factor: N/A

The LiDAR datasets have the following properties:

- File format: LAS
- Point density: ~4300 pts / m²
- Coordinate system: EPSG 4326 – WGS84 reference ellipsoid
- Point attributes: number of returns, return number, GPS time, intensity
- Scale factor x, y, z: 0.001, 0.001, 0.001

4.3 WP deliverables

D-1 Report on the SRIX4Veg fieldwork activities

D-2 Report on the contribution to the development of good practice guidelines

D-3 Data: orthorectified surface reflectance products of agricultural sites

All deliverables are available on the Zenodo portal as per:

Smigaj, M., van der Zee, J., Bartholomeus, H., & Kooistra, L. (2024). IDEAS-QA4EO WP-2520: Support to SRIX4Veg. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8211058>

Appendix A

Figure A1. Comparison between image-derived reflectance factor (solid lines) and field spectrometer measurements (dashed lines) of ground calibration targets following empirical line calibration for: flight 1 under Protocol 1 (*left*) and flight 3 under Protocol 1 (*right*). Note: two Permaflect targets were not available in the dataset collected during flight 1.

Figure A2. Comparison between image-derived reflectance factor (solid lines) and field spectrometer measurements (dashed lines) of ground calibration targets following empirical line calibration for flight 3 under Protocol 2.

Figure A3. A sample RGB subset of a flightline impacted by the sensor malfunctioning during flight 2 of Protocol 2 showcasing the abnormal behaviour (*left*), alongside radiance values of example vegetated pixels measured outside (green) and inside (violet) the impacted area (*right*).

Table A1. Pixel-level absolute differences in reflectance factor between imagery with and without VZA-based filtering employed. The values were obtained at Sentinel-2 spatial resolution following spectral convolution and spatial aggregation.

Sentinel-2 band	Minimum	Maximum	Average
2	0.000	0.230	0.076
3	0.004	0.434	0.134
4	0.006	0.252	0.095
5	0.006	0.479	0.174
6	0.018	1.553	0.525
7	0.006	2.408	0.726
8	0.049	2.430	0.763
9	0.097	2.135	0.713
8A	0.029	2.268	0.782